

Data management plan project "Knots in Clay: Insights into Ancient Fibrework from Imprints in Pottery"

Version 1

Description

Data management plan for the data generated in the project "Knots in Clay: Insights into Ancient Fibrework from Imprints in Pottery" implemented by Valdis Bērziņš, Institute of Latvian History, Faculty of Humanities, University of Latvia, Sept 2024 - Feb 2026

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia"

Researchers

Valdis Berzins (0000-0003-3991-5147)

Organizations
University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data management plan project "Knots in Clay: Insights into Ancient Fibrework from Imprints in Pottery"

Description:

Data management plan for the data generated in the project "Knots in Clay: Insights into Ancient Fibrework from Imprints in Pottery" implemented by Valdis Bērziņš, Institute of Latvian History, Faculty of Humanities, University of Latvia, Sept 2024 - Feb 2026

Researchers:

Valdis Berzins (0000-0003-3991-5147)

Organizations:

University of Latvia

Contact: Bērziņš Valdis (valdis.berzins@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia"

Project: Knots in Clay: Insights into Ancient Fibrework from Imprints in Pottery (LU-BA-ZG-2024/1-0012)

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Dataset of observations and identified techniques of knot and plait imprints in Neolithic pottery from western Latvia

Dataset of descriptive textual and measurement data and identified techniques of knot and plait imprints in Neolithic pottery from western Latvia, as observed stereomicroscopically

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

analysis

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Observation data
- Other

Includes identifications of techniques used to create imprints

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 200

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No data stored in repositories appropriate for re-use.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers studying the techniques of archaeological pottery decoration or prehistoric cordage/textiles

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata identifying the researcher, the project, the purpose of the analysis, the methods used and the archaeological collections analysed

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

Can be opened with many open source software applications.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

From funding allocated to project.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Valdis Berzins (0000-0003-3991-5147)

All tasks undertaken by Valdis Bērziņš

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

No additional costs envisaged after project realization.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

Dataset of macro- and microphotographs of knot and plait imprints in Neolithic pottery from western Latvia

Dataset of macro- and microphotographs of knot and plait imprints in Neolithic pottery from western Latvia

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

analysis

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No data stored in repositories appropriate for re-use.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers studying the techniques of archaeological pottery decoration or prehistoric cordage/textiles

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

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Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata identifying the researcher, the project, the purpose of the analysis, the methods used and the archaeological collections analysed

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

Can be opened with many open source software applications.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Many open source software applications

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

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No additional costs envisaged after project realization.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

Dataset of reflectance transformation images of knot and plait imprints in Neolithic pottery from western Latvia

Dataset of reflectance transformation images of knot and plait imprints in Neolithic pottery from western Latvia

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

analysis

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

RTI

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No data stored in repositories appropriate for re-use.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers studying the techniques of archaeological pottery decoration or prehistoric cordage/textiles

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2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

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No

Metadata identifying the researcher, the project, the purpose of the analysis, the methods used and the archaeological collections analysed

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

RTIViewer

https://www.c-h-i.org/learn/learn_RTIViewer_download.html

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

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From funding allocated to project.

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All tasks undertaken by Valdis Bērziņš

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

No additional costs envisaged after project realization.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

Dataset of observations from experiments to replicate knot and plait impressions

Dataset of observations from experiments undertaken to replicate knot and plait impressions in pottery, for comparison with archaeological data

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

analysis

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 200

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No data stored in repositories appropriate for re-use.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers studying the techniques of archaeological pottery decoration or prehistoric cordage/textiles

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata identifying the researcher, the project, the purpose of the analysis, the methods used and the archaeological collections analysed

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

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Can be opened with many open source software applications.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

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2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

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No

Dataset of macro- and microphotographs of replicated knot and plait impressions

Dataset of macro- and microphotographs of replicated knot and plait impressions, for comparison with archaeological data

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?
analysis

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

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Dataset of reflectance transformation images of replicated knot and plait impressions, for comparison with archaeological data

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

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1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?
analysis

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

RTI

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

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Researchers studying the techniques of archaeological pottery decoration or prehistoric cordage/textiles

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3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

Dataset of AMS radiocarbon datings

Dataset of AMS radiocarbon datings from samples from sites with analysed knot and plait decoration on pottery

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

analysis

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 200

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No data stored in repositories appropriate for re-use.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers studying the Neolithic of Latvia and the Baltic Sea region.

Researchers studying the techniques of archaeological pottery decoration or prehistoric cordage/textiles

2 Research Data Management

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